

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 8: Supportive Tools for the Experimentation module and Creating Screenshots

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This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.01 (Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.3.8).

Abstract

This tutorial showcases an update to the Experimentation and Visualization modules that introduces two supportive tools for results processing and allows for automated plot screenshot generation.

Keywords: JECDM, experimentation tools, screenshot

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1. Introduction [T]

Source package:
`t1_t10.t8_experimentation_tools_and_screenshots`

This tutorial (update) introduces a few minor updates to the Experimentation and Visualization module:

- Experimentation module: Two useful tools for processing results are added: *LatexTableFromXLSX* and *ConvergencePlotFromXLSX* (see *Experimentation.tools* package). The first assists in parsing tabular data stored in an Excel file into a Latex code (table), while the latter helps in creating convergence plots from Excel data.
- Visualization module: A method for automatically creating plot render and saving it as a *BufferedImage* object is introduced.

This update includes three sub-tutorials that are briefly discussed in what follows. Note that, however, the codes and their use are relatively straightforward. Therefore, they are not brought here for the sake of conciseness.

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2. LatexTableFromXLSX tool

Source package:
`t1_t10.t8_experimentation_tools_and_screenshots`
`t1_latex_from_excel`

This brief tutorial introduces the *LatexTableFromXLSX* tool. It assists in creating a Latex table-related code from tabular data stored in an Excel file (XLSX format). Consider Figure 1. It illustrates one of this tutorial's cases. The table presents some fictitious data summarizing the performance of two algorithms: *M1* and *M2*. The *LatexTableFromXLSX* tool allows loading the selected sub-table from this first sheet and building its representation as a Latex code. Note that the tool allows for specifying, e.g., vertical/horizontal line placement or selecting cells to be merged as a multi-column or multi-row. The expected Latex code is illustrated in Figure 2. Finally, the produced table is in Table 1.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1								
2		Measure		M1		M2		
3		Algorithm	Problem	Min	Max	Min	Mean	Max
4		A1	P1	0,2	0,5	0,1	0,5	0,6
5			P2	0,7	0,9	0,3	0,4	0,5
6		A2	P1	0,1	0,4	0,3	0,6	0,7
7			P2	0,8	0,9	0,1	0,2	0,3
8			P3	0,1	0,2	0,4	0,5	0,9
9								
10								
11								

Figure 1: Example input stored in Excel file – creating a Latex table

```

Printing table no. 0 =====
\begin{tabular}{|c|c|c|c|c|c|c|}
\hline{*7}{-}
\multicolumn{2}{|c|}{Measure} & \multicolumn{2}{|c|}{M1} & \multicolumn{3}{|c|}{M2} \\
\hline{*7}{-}
Algorithm & Problem & Min & Max & Min & Mean & Max \\
\hline{*7}{-}
\multirow{2}{*}{A1} & P1 & 0.20 & 0.50 & 0.100 & 0.500 & 0.600 \\
& P2 & 0.70 & 0.90 & 0.300 & 0.400 & 0.500 \\
\hline{*7}{-}
\multirow{3}{*}{A2} & P1 & 0.10 & 0.40 & 0.300 & 0.600 & 0.700 \\
& P2 & 0.80 & 0.90 & 0.100 & 0.200 & 0.300 \\
& P3 & 0.10 & 0.20 & 0.400 & 0.500 & 0.900 \\
\hline{*7}{-}
\end{tabular}

```

Figure 2: Generated latex code

Table 1: TEST 1

Measure		M1		M2		
Algorithm	Problem	Min	Max	Min	Mean	Max
A1	P1	0.20	0.50	0.100	0.500	0.600
	P2	0.70	0.90	0.300	0.400	0.500
A2	P1	0.10	0.40	0.300	0.600	0.700
	P2	0.80	0.90	0.100	0.200	0.300
	P3	0.10	0.20	0.400	0.500	0.900

Figure 4: Expected convergence plot

3. ConvergencePlotFromXLSX tool

```

Source package:
t1_t10.t8_experimentation_tools_and_screenshots.
t2_convergence_plot_from_excel

```

While *LatexTableFromXLSX* derives Latex tables from an Excel file, *ConvergencePlotFromXLSX* helps constructing convergence plots from such data (XLSX format). An example input data of this tutorial is presented in Figure 3. Note that the data to be illustrated must be stored as columns. The expected plot is depicted in Figure 4

	A	B	C	D	E
1	X	Y	STD	Y	STD
2	0	100	10	100	30
3	1	99	10	90	30
4	2	98	10	85,8578644	30
5	3	97	10	82,6794919	30
6	4	96	10	80	30
7	5	95	10	77,6393202	30
8	6	94	10	75,5051026	30
9	7	93	10	73,5424869	30
10	8	92	10	71,7157288	30
11	9	91	10	70	30
12	10	90	10	68,3772234	30
13	11	89	10	66,8337521	30
14	12	88	10	65,3589838	30
15	13	87	10	63,9444872	30
16	14	86	10	62,5834261	30
17	15	85	10	61,2701665	30
18	16	84	10	60	30

Figure 3: Example input stored in Excel file – creating a convergence plot

4. Saving plot render as BufferedImage

```

Source package:
t1_t10.t8_experimentation_tools_and_screenshots.
t2_convergence_plot_from_excel.Tutorial2b and
t1_t10.t8_experimentation_tools_and_screenshots.
t3_3D_screenshot

```

This tutorial demonstrates constructing a plot screenshot, represented as *BufferedImage* object. Note that the image size can be set arbitrarily, independently of the plot frame size (the frame may not even be set visible). Also, the screenshot generation is synchronous. When requested, the invoking code is given a *CountDownLatch* barrier and its *.await()* method should be called. If it is not, the render generation may be completed only partially before, e.g., storing the image as a file. The expected images generated in these two tutorials are illustrated in Figures 5 and Figures 6.

Figure 5: Expected render (Tutorial2b)

Figure 6: Expected render (Tutorial3)